

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF TRAFFIC FLOW AND WEATHER CONDITIONS ON ROAD SAFETY (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE FERGANA VALLEY)

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Abstract. The total number of vehicles in the republic is more than 3 million. Currently, according to the State Statistics Committee, in 2010 - 21, in 2015 - 42, and in January-September 2020, there are 48 passenger cars per 100 households [1]. The most densely populated regions in our republic today are Tashkent city, Samarkand, Fergana, Namangan, Andijan, Kashkadarya, Bukhara and Khorezm regions. That is, the Fergana Valley is one of the most densely populated and connected regions of the republic in terms of road network.

Keywords: traffic flow, traffic speed, traffic density, traffic volume, weather and climate, road conditions, level of danger, road fogging, road accidents.

Introduction.

The territory of the Fergana Valley is 19.2 thousand km², or 4.2%. The valley includes the regions of "Andijan, Fergana, Namangan". Including the total length of the road network of our Republic is 209496 km, of which the Fergana Valley road network accounts for 23%, the road network density is 2327 km/1000 km², and the population density is 525.1 thousand people/1000 km². Aims to assess the impact of traffic flow and weather conditions on road safety.

The purpose of road zoning of traffic flow on public roads in the Fergana Valley according to the level of danger is to ensure traffic safety on highways, taking into account the traffic flow situation, road conditions, and weather and climatic factors.

Traffic density is measured as the number of vehicles per 1 km of traffic lane (q-km/unit). This indicator varies depending on the traffic composition, its speed, and road conditions.

Figure 1. Graph of changes in traffic flow density in the Fergana Valley.

Methodology.

It should be noted from the above figure that the traffic flow on highways varies depending on the speed of movement. 5-7 cars/km move at speeds of 97 km/h, 7-11 cars/km at speeds of 85 km/h, and 12-17 cars/km at speeds of 58 km/h. Changes in the volume and composition of vehicles on highways lead to changes in speeds, the occurrence of road traffic accidents on roads, and an increase in the level of traffic danger. The A-373 highway consists of a 586 km long road along the route "M39 highway - Gulistan - Buka - Angren - Kokand and Andijan - Osh" and is a major highway that carries passengers and cargo from the main valley to the capital and the region.

The 4R112 highway is 305 km long on the "Fergana Ring Road" route. It is a highway connecting the "Andijan - Fergana - Namangan" regions and is a major road intended for interregional passenger transportation. Taking into account the high traffic volume of the A-373 and 4R112 highways, it is necessary to identify road traffic accidents occurring on the roads and determine the level of traffic danger in the areas where they occur using the safety coefficient.

According to the State Statistics Committee, road transport is leading in the structure of passenger transportation by type of transport in 2020. Its share in the total volume of passenger transportation is 99.3%. The regions with the highest share of the total volume of passengers transported by road are: Tashkent city - 19.0%, Andijan region - 12.5%, Tashkent region - 11.4%, Fergana region - 11.4%. We determine the safety coefficient of vehicles on the Fergana Valley highway using the formula below.

Figure 2. Dynamics of changes in safety of the 4R112 highway section

The 180-185 km section of the 4R112 "Fergana Ring Road" category II highway, passing through the city of Asaka and the Kuva district, is considered a very dangerous area. This area passes through a residential area, is densely populated, and various types of household shops are located along the roadside. As the density of the traffic flow increases, the distance between vehicles decreases, the speed decreases, the psychological work regime of drivers becomes more difficult, and the general traffic is inconvenient. According to the results of the analysis, it was determined that the hazard level of sections 190-305 km of the 4R112 "Fergana Ring Road" is a hazardous area..

$$K_h = V_{kis}/V_{kir}; \tag{1}$$

When determining dangerous sections of a road with a safety coefficient, the values in Table 1 are used. [2].

1- Table

Safety factor	$\leq 0,4$	0,4-0,6	0,6-0,8	$\geq 0,8$
Roadway hazard level	Very dangerous	Dangerous	Less dangerous	Practically safe

Figure 3 shows an analysis of traffic accidents on highway 4R112 passing through the Fergana Valley.

We have determined the quantitative indicators of road traffic accidents that occurred in the last three years on the 4R112 "Fergana Ring Road" public highway in the Fergana Valley. Compared to 2018, in 2020, an analysis of the number of accidents occurring on the 4R112 "Fergana Ring Road" highway (PK) showed that there were more accidents such as collisions, hitting barriers, running over pedestrians, and hitting bicycles.

The climatic conditions of the Fergana Valley are determined by its distance from the ocean, which makes the climate sharply continental and dry. The nature of the valley is beautiful and fascinating, rich in delicacies, a paradise, it is called the "jewel of Central Asia" [3]. The Fergana Valley is surrounded by mountains, which prevent the direct passage of cold air masses blowing from the north and northeast and moist air masses blowing from the west. The summer in the Fergana Valley is hot and dry, with an average temperature of +26 +27°C in July, and the hottest temperature reaching +43 +44°C. The vegetation period in the Fergana Valley lasts 230-240 days, and the total temperature is 4400-4800°C.

The average winter, summer, and annual temperatures in Fergana are lower than in many parts of Uzbekistan. For example, the average annual temperature in Tashkent is 13.3° C, in Mirzachul 13.2° C, in Termez 17.0° C, in Bukhara 15.1° C, in Karshi 15.8° C, and in the Fergana Valley 13.0° C. Climatologists [12, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 90] have divided the climate of the Fergana Valley into warm and cold periods (Fig. 4). Days with an average daily temperature exceeding +5°C are included in the warm period, and days with a temperature below +5°C are included in the cold period. The warm period is divided into early spring (S, +5°C≤T≤+20°C), mid-summer (Sum, T>+20°C) and late autumn (Au, +20°C≤T≤+5°C), while the cold period corresponds to the winter (W, T<+5°C).

Figure 4. Seasonal periods of the year in the Fergana Valley according to traffic conditions

Results and discussion. In the climatic conditions of the Fergana Valley, the winter period is characterized by precipitation, low air temperature and moderate humidity, gusty winds, and the surface of the pavement is in a state of damp, wet, mud, snow, ice, slush and microslush, with the unexpected occurrence of precipitation, short-term slush and microslush, and morning fog, while the summer period is characterized by high air temperature and low air humidity, sunny days, gusty winds, dust and dust on the surface of the pavement.

Weather and climate factors – indicators of the “Environment” system of the “Driver-Vehicle-Road-Environment” (DVRE) system. The following weather and climate conditions have the greatest negative impact on road safety: low air temperature, various types of precipitation, strong wind, low atmospheric pressure, high humidity, fog, ice. Natural and climatic factors and bad weather and climate conditions lead to a significant increase in road accidents. From the above data, we can say that in bad weather conditions, the number of minor accidents between road users increases several times [4,5].

Let's look at the impact of climatic factors on road safety. As a rule, weather conditions are associated with the seasons (Figure 6).

Determining the weight of the road network and traffic safety indicators.

2-table

Provinces	P _{to.ysh}	Number of private vehicles	K _{yth}	P _{ys.hx.}
Andijan	0,41	223783	0,55	0,75
Namangan	0,45	218613	0,35	1,30
Fergana	0,35	325009	0,45	0,78

Based on the data in Table 2, the boundaries of the districts were determined based on the weight of the regional road network and traffic safety. The boundaries of the districts of the Fergana region in terms of the road network and traffic safety are shown in the graph below (Figure 5) and the data is presented in the table (Table 2).

Conclusions and recommendations. These conclusions were reached based on the above information:

-the following measures can be proposed to minimize the negative impact of weather and climatic factors on road safety:

- maintaining high traction of the road surface throughout the year, preventing its wetting, freezing and de-icing;

- cleaning roads from dirt and snow;
- installing lighting devices in the most dangerous areas, including outside populated areas;
- providing driver orientation on roads during foggy periods and equipping them with lighting devices.

Figure 5. District boundaries for road network and traffic safety

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